

LLM-Powered Knowledge Graphs vs Topic Modelling for Sustainable Development Analytics

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Abstract. Knowledge Graphs (KGs) are increasingly recognised as effective tools for structuring complex sustainability information and supporting Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG)-aligned decision-making. This paper presents a comparative study between two approaches applied to sustainability analytics: (1) topic extraction using Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI), and (2) GenAI-driven KG construction using Neo4j’s Large Language Model (LLM) Graph Builder (GB).

We apply both methods to a hybrid dataset comprising International Monetary Fund (IMF) Global Financial Stability Reports (GFSRs) and Greenstone ESG newsletters. While prior studies have leveraged topic modelling to identify thematic patterns in alignment with the United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), our approach extends this by generating semantic graphs that explicitly capture entities, relationships, and development themes.

Our findings demonstrate that GenAI-based KG construction provides more structured, interpretable, and actionable representations than topic modelling alone. These results highlight the potential of LLM-powered KGs to enhance transparency, insight generation, and alignment with SDGs—particularly in underrepresented domains such as the social and governance pillars of ESG.

Keywords: Generative AI · Knowledge Graphs · Sustainable Development · ESG Analytics · Large Language Models.

1 Introduction

Global progress toward the SDGs remains insufficient. The 2024 SDG Progress Report [19] indicates that only 17% of targets are on track for 2030, 34 lack sufficient trend data, and over one-third of indicators have no recent data. Goals 5 (Gender Equality), 13 (Climate Action), and 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions) face particularly serious implementation and monitoring gaps. These challenges underscore the need for better data integration and advanced analytics to support timely, context-aware sustainability decisions.

Recent advances in AI-driven topic modelling have enhanced the extraction of insights from complex sustainability texts. Prior studies have applied

topic modeling to SDG research [13], societal belief analysis [20], and LLM-enhanced discourse mapping [9]. Frameworks like LangChain support these applications by enabling LLM-based pipelines for summarization, entity extraction, and retrieval-augmented generation [11, 16, 23, 4].

However, prompt design remains a core challenge in LLM-based topic modeling [8, 17]. To address this, we employed the MIPROv2 optimiser [12], a Bayesian-based prompt tuning method, which significantly improved semantic coherence in ESG topic outputs.

Despite these advancements, most studies still focus on single-source analysis and do not integrate heterogeneous sustainability data sources. This leaves a gap in understanding how global ESG priorities are interpreted and applied at a local level, particularly for Social and Governance pillars, which require contextual nuance and human interpretation.

Recent advances in AI increasingly leverage KG to improve explainability, integrate domain knowledge, and support decision-making. KGs enhance the transparency and trustworthiness of machine learning by providing machine-readable background knowledge [18]. A cognitive KG that models Theory of Mind (ToM) to represent complex human behaviours and mental processes extend this idea [21].

In sustainability research, KGs support the management of heterogeneous data and the interpretation of complex ESG information. [2] highlights that the modularity and semantic reasoning capabilities of KGs allow for flexible integration of multiple standards. [10] emphasises that interpretability is a core strength of KGs—one that can enhance their adoption in sustainability decision-making by increasing stakeholder trust. Several studies apply design-oriented approaches to ESG knowledge modeling, such as ESG metric extraction and the demonstration of dynamic metric integration using KGs [3, 15, 22, 1]. Furthermore, the OpenAI-powered hierarchical ESG taxonomy, ESGSenticNet, outperforms standard NLP lexicons by addressing challenges such as subjectivity, immateriality, and complexity [14].

Despite these advancements, the use of KGs to integrate heterogeneous ESG data—particularly for the Social and Governance pillars—remains limited. These areas require nuanced, human-readable interpretations. A rare example is the work by Gyrard et al. [7], who developed a mental health KG aligned with SDG 3, showing how domain-specific KGs can support targeted development goals through semantic enrichment and decision support.

This points to a research gap: while GenAI and KGs offer individual strengths, their combined potential to structure diverse ESG data into actionable, interpretable insights—especially for social and governance-focused SDG targets—remains underexplored.

2 Methodology

This study follows a comparative design to evaluate OpenAI-powered topic modelling and KG construction using structured and unstructured documents relevant to sustainability and ESGs.

2.1 Data Collection

The structured corpus comprises 41 GFSRs published by IMF between 2003 and 2023. These documents provide macroeconomic analysis, financial risk assessments, and regulatory insights. The unstructured corpus includes 62 ESG-focused newsletters published on LinkedIn by Greenstone between 2022 and 2023. These newsletters [6] offer practitioner-driven insights on sustainability strategies, regulatory changes, and sectoral developments. Greenstone’s reputation, including recognition of its InvestorPortal ESG software as *Sustainability Product of the Year* in 2020, motivated its selection for this study [5].

We extracted documents using Python-based scraping tools: *pdfreader* for structured data, *Selenium* and *BeautifulSoup4* for unstructured data. We chose this dual-source design to facilitate a comparative investigation into how thematic insights and relational structures differ between structured and unstructured sustainability-related content.

2.2 Data Preprocessing

We applied minimal preprocessing to both datasets to preserve semantic richness. Our cleaning process involved removing HTML tags. We intentionally avoided tokenization and lemmatization to maintain document structure and contextual integrity, which are essential for LLM-based analysis.

This strategy ensured consistency across both the topic modelling and KG construction pipelines, allowing the models to interpret the data with its original context intact.

2.3 Topic Modelling Pipeline

We used OpenAI’s GPT-4o-mini model to extract context-aware topics from datasets. After evaluating multiple models, we found it to be the most effective for generating semantically rich and coherent topic outputs. To further improve topic quality, we incorporated the DSPy MIPROv2 optimiser [12]. This pipeline automatically tuned the prompt structure and selected optimal few-shot examples using Bayesian search and gives the optimal instruction. By this step, we significantly improved the semantic coherence, topical diversity, and alignment of the extracted topics with key sustainability and SDG themes. We used the resulting optimised topics as a baseline for evaluating semantic coverage and insight quality in comparison to the outputs of the KG construction workflow.

2.4 Knowledge Graph Construction with Neo4j LLM Graph Builder

We used Neo4j’s LLM GB, powered by OpenAI’s GPT-4o-mini, to construct KG from data sources. We uploaded the documents into a Neo4j Aura instance via the GB portal. The system then automatically extracted entities such as organizations, sectors, and policy instruments, and instantiated semantic relationships based on contextual dependencies inferred by the underlying language model.

To support modality-specific analysis, we enriched each node with metadata fields including the file name and source type. We then queried the generated graphs using Cypher to identify structural patterns, focusing on entities related to responsible authorities, organizations, and recommended actions. This approach allowed us to prepare the graph outputs for direct comparison with the topics extracted from the topic modelling pipeline.

3 Results and Discussion

This section presents the comparative findings of the GenAI based topic modelling and KG construction methods applied to datasets. The goal is to evaluate how each method captures thematic, sectoral, and authority-related insights relevant to sustainability and ESG decision-making.

3.1 Topic Modelling Outcomes

The structured dataset primarily revealed themes related to macro-financial conditions, monetary policy, and financial market risks, whereas the unstructured emphasised practical ESG actions, such as carbon reporting, data verification, and commitments to sustainability (Table 1). This divergence illustrates a thematic gap between high-level policy discourse and operational ESG practices. However, while the topics provided a high-level overview of themes (in Figure 1), the topic modelling method did not capture the underlying relationships between entities, such as which sectors were associated with specific authorities or which actions were taken in particular territories. This limitation made it difficult to map the results to decision-making contexts where actionable connections—such as responsible institutions or regional policy relevance—are essential.

We manually categorized topics into conceptual clusters such as territories, sectors, and authorities (Table 2). Although these clusters surfaced distinct patterns (e.g., structured data focusing on IMF, Basel, and macroeconomic territories; unstructured data reflecting local community issues and procurement practices), the topic modelling method lacked the relational depth to express how these elements interact in practice.

3.2 Knowledge Graph Results

Unlike topic modelling, the GB explicitly extracted entities and relationships, producing interpretable triples that represent domain-specific knowledge. We

Fig. 1. Word Cloud Representation of Extracted Topics from Structured and Unstructured Data

Table 1. Topic samples extracted by GenAI from structured and unstructured data, showcasing key themes in sustainability, ESG, financial stability, and regulatory frameworks.

Data Source	Topic
Structured	Global Economic Outlook, Monetary Policy, Financial Markets, Regional Economic Performance, Risks and Vulnerabilities, Corporate Financial Health, Housing Market Trends, Sector-Specific Concerns
Unstructured	Environmental Sustainability, Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP), CDP Reporting Practices, Momentum in Reporting, Data Assurance, Approval Processes, Data Coverage, Commitments to Sustainability

Table 2. Topic clusters by territories, sectors, and authorities.

Category	Data Source	Topics
Territories	Unstructured	South Africa (Countries in South Africa), European Sustainability, Local Communities
	Structured	Emerging Market Economies, Global Financial, Shock Countries, Euro Area Periphery
Sectors	Unstructured	Supply Chain, Procurement
	Structured	Banking, Real Estate, Asset Management Industries, Supply Chain, Corporate Bond Markets
Authorities	Unstructured	Non-financial Reporting Directive, Responsible Reporting, Reporting Directory, Policymakers
	Structured	Policymakers, Sustainability Reporting Directive (SRD), Non-financial Reporting Directive (NFRD), Basel Community

obtained a structured representation of the ESG landscape, with the model extracting entities, assigning labels, and linking them via semantic relations. For example, it grouped entities under labels using the `HAS_ENTITY` relationship, such as `Characteristic`, `Action`, and `Organization`. These connections provide interpretable insights directly applicable to ESG authority and sector mapping. One such relationship—`HAS_CHARACTERISTIC` → “unsustainable returns”—shows how specific institutions may be associated with sector-level financial vulnera-

bilities, while `USE_BUFFERS` → “capital and liquidity buffers” reflects regulatory interventions addressing those risks (see Table 3). This graph-based representa-

Table 3. Selected KG triples for the `banks` entity extracted using Neo4j’s LLM Graph Builder. (Result of Cypher query: `MATCH path = (e:Entity:Organization {id:"banks"})-[x]->(r) RETURN e.id, type(x) AS Relationship, r.id AS Entity`)

Source Entity	Relationship	Target Entity
banks	<code>EXTEND_CREDIT_TO</code>	risky borrowers
	<code>HAS_CHARACTERISTIC</code>	unsustainable returns
	<code>USE_BUFFERS</code>	capital and liquidity buffers
	<code>EXPOSE_TO</code>	external shocks
	<code>REPRESENT</code>	systemic financial agents

tion improves traceability, human readability, and decision support by explicitly linking entities to roles, attributes, and behaviours. These structured outputs align more naturally with sustainable development monitoring frameworks and help stakeholders navigate complex ESG landscapes more effectively.

4 Conclusion

This paper presented a comparative study of AI-driven topic modelling and LLM-based KG construction for sustainability-related document analysis. We examined both structured and unstructured data to evaluate how an OpenAI-powered topic extraction pipeline compares with Neo4j’s LLM GB in capturing semantic insights.

The results indicate that while topic models produce semantically meaningful clusters, they lack explicit relational structures and often require additional interpretation. In contrast, the KG approach yields richer, more interpretable outputs by directly linking entities and concepts through contextual relationships. This enhances explainability and aligns more naturally with policy frameworks and SDG priorities, particularly in underrepresented social and governance domains.

Our findings suggest that LLM-based KG offers a scalable and transparent solution for multi-source sustainability analysis. Future work will focus on expanding cross-domain datasets, improving graph evaluation metrics, and integrating SDG alignment scoring to better support policy-driven decision-making.

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